

A Review of Smart Generation and WINBO Energy Method

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Introduction

A wind turbine, or alternatively referred to as a wind energy converter, is a device that converts the wind's kinetic energy into electrical energy. [1] Wind turbines are manufactured in a wide range of vertical and horizontal axis. The smallest turbines are used for applications such as battery charging for auxiliary power for boats or caravans or to power traffic warning signs. Larger turbines can be used for making contributions to a domestic power supply while selling unused power back to the utility supplier via the electrical grid. Arrays of large turbines, known as wind farms, are becoming an increasingly important source of intermittent renewable energy and are used by many countries as part of a strategy to reduce their reliance on fossil fuels. One assessment claimed that, as of 2009, wind had the "lowest relative greenhouse gas emissions, the least water consumption demands and... the most favorable social impacts" compared to photovoltaic, hydro, geothermal, coal and gas. [2]. If we use the physical source instead of the source (wind) of wind energy then we can produce the same efficiency of electricity, and this will not harm the environment, and in today's times we need the most pure power by which we can strengthen the economic condition of our country and save our ecosystem, and the dream of our smart city and bullet train can come true. With this step we will move one step forward from the world. This project can protect the cow-bull that roams around the roads. We can also provide security, shelter, food to them. If they keep on walking on the open road then their condition will get worse every day. With the intent of roaming the cow, he

Abstract

WINBO energy method is the upgrade of old technology. This technique is created by mixing the new technology with the old technology. To make this technique, some changes were made in the wind energy method, such major changes in sources (Ox power replace wind energy) and some changes in the system to run accordingly Ox speed. Speed of turbine is managed using gear box, turbine needs 15 km/hr speed. This paper has analysis of generation of electricity using wind energy method.

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comes on the road and collides with the vehicle, both of them suffer loss. As a physical source, the ox should be used according to me. Because their use in farm is stopped, the machine is being used at their place and now their owners have left them on the road because they are now for their master not working. And they are now engaged in saving their existence. The ox has been used by our ancestors since time to time. They used to be used anywhere, like plough, pulling water well, pulling ox car, doing other things. Because of the same reasons, I think that wind energy we can use the ox instead of the source of the air.

Literature Review

Why Winbo Energy Method Required?

- We need renewable resources like solar
- Winbo is also a type of renewable resources
- It produces electricity from modified wind power plant.
- It is economical.
- It is beneficial for cows and bull.

Working Principle

What is ox Turbine?

Ox turbine is a modified version of vertical axis wind turbine (HAWT). Vertical-axis wind turbines (or VAWTs) have the main rotor shaft arranged vertically. One advantage of this arrangement is that the turbine does not need to be pointed into the wind to be effective, which is an advantage on a site where the wind direction is highly variable. It is also an advantage when the turbine is integrated into a building because it is inherently less steerable. Also, the generator and gearbox can be placed near the ground, using a direct drive from the rotor assembly to the ground-based gearbox, improving accessibility for maintenance. However, these designs produce much less energy averaged over time, which is a major drawback. [3][4]

The key disadvantages include the relatively low rotational speed with the consequential higher torque and hence higher cost of the drive train, the inherently lower power coefficient, the 360-degree rotation of the aerofoil within the wind flow during each cycle and hence the highly dynamic loading on the blade, the pulsating torque generated by some rotor designs on the drive train, and the difficulty of modeling the wind flow accurately and hence the challenges of analyzing and designing the rotor prior to fabricating a prototype. [5]

When a turbine is mounted on a rooftop the building generally redirects wind over the roof and this can double the wind speed at the turbine. If the height of a rooftop mounted turbine tower is approximately 50% of the building height it is near the optimum for maximum wind energy and minimum wind turbulence. While wind speeds within the built environment are generally much lower than at exposed rural sites, [6] [7] noise may be a concern and an existing structure may not adequately resist the additional stress.

Figure:1 Wind Energy Module

How Can Generate Electricity Using Ox Turbine?

Ox turbine converts kinetic energy to generate electrical or mechanical strength. It is done using a turbine, which usually has propellers; To generate electricity turbine can be connected to a generator, or ox power is used as a mechanical power which acts as a machine to pull the water with the help of a pump and grinding the grain. Since OX runs around the turbine, it transports blades, which rotates shaft. Currently there is single type of turbine in use in this system vertical axis wind turbine (VAWT). VAWT is not general turbine, it is which displays the propeller or most fan style blades. [8]

Converting Ox Power to Mechanical Energy

Ox turbines convert the kinetic energy from the Ox power into mechanical power. The rotor is connected to the generator, either directly (if it's a direct drive turbine) or through a shaft and a series of gears (a gearbox) that speed up the rotation and allow for a physically smaller generator. [9]

Ox power is converted by the blades of ox turbine. The blades of the Ox turbines are designed in single way that is called drag type.

Drag type: this blade design uses the force of the ox power to push the blades around. These blades have a higher torque than lift designs but with a slower rotating speed. As the rotating speed of the blades are slower. [10]

Creating Electricity from Ox Power

To create electricity from ox power the shaft of the turbine must be connected to a generator. The Ox generator uses the turning motion of the shaft to rotate a rotor which has oppositely charge magnets and is among copper wire loops. Electromagnetic induction is created by the rotor twirl the inside of the core, generating electricity. [11]

Distribution of Electricity

The electricity produced by harnessing the Ox's power mechanical energy must go through a

transformer in order rise its voltage and transfer it to long distance successfully. Power stations and fuse box receive current and then turn it into a low voltage, which can be used safely by business and homes. [12]

Comparison of fossil-fuel turbines with wind turbine (Ox turbine)

Advantages

Wind turbines are generally inexpensive. They will produce electricity at between two and six cents per kilowatt hour, which is one of the lowest-priced renewable energy sources. As technology needed for wind turbines continues to improve, the prices will decrease as well. In addition, there is no competitive market for wind energy, as it does not cost money to get a hold of wind. [20] The main cost of wind turbines are the installation process. The average cost is between \$48,000 and \$65,000 to install. However, the energy harvested from the turbine will offset the installation cost, as well as provide virtually free energy for years after. [13]

Wind turbines provide a clean energy source, emitting no greenhouse gases and no waste product. Over 1,500 tons of carbon dioxide per year can be eliminated by using a one megawatt turbine instead of one megawatt of energy from a fossil fuel.[14] Being environmentally friendly and green is a large advantage of wind turbines.

Disadvantages

Wind turbines can be very large, reaching over 140 meters (460 ft) tall and with blades 55 meters (60 yd) long, and people have often complained about their visual impact. [15]

Environmental impact of wind turbine includes effect on wildlife, but can be mitigated if proper monitoring and mitigation strategies are implemented. [16] Thousands of birds, including rare species, have been killed by the blades of wind turbines, [17] though wind turbines contribute relatively insignificantly to anthropogenic avian mortality. For every bird killed by a wind turbine in the US, nearly 500,000 are killed by each of feral cats and buildings. [18] In comparison, conventional coal fired generators contribute significantly more to bird mortality, by incineration when caught in updrafts of smoke stacks and by poisoning with emissions byproducts (including particulates and heavy metals downwind of flue gases). Further, marine life is affected by water intakes of steam turbine cooling towers (heat exchangers) for nuclear and fossil fuel generators, by coal dust deposits in marine ecosystems (e.g. damaging Australia's Great Barrier Reef) and by water acidification from combustion monoxides. [19]

Energy harnessed by wind turbines is intermittent, and is not a "dispatch able" source of power; its availability is based on whether the wind is blowing, not whether electricity is needed. Turbines can be placed on ridges or bluffs to maximize the access of wind they have, but this also limits the locations where they can be placed. In this way, wind energy is not a particularly reliable source of energy. However, it can form part of the energy mix, which also includes power from other sources. Notably, the relative available output from wind and solar sources is often inversely proportional (balancing). Technology is also being developed to store excess energy, which can then make up for any deficits in supplies.